
Links between needs of EMA and One Health EJP expertise

**WP5 Science to policy
translation to stakeholders**

Responsible Partner: BfR, SSI

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LINKS BETWEEN NEEDS OF EMA AND ONE HEALTH EJP EXPERTISE

Introduction

[The One Health European Joint Programme](#) (One Health EJP) aims to create a sustainable European framework by integration and alignment of medical, veterinary and food safety institutes that perform reference laboratory functions. The organisations unite forces through joint prioritization and conduction of research, integrative activities, and training and education exercises in the domains of foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging threats, thus matching the needs of European and national policy makers and stakeholders. Through this One Health approach, the consortium strengthens its preparedness according to the 'prevent-detect-response' concept.

All One Health EJP partners have the mandate of their national or regional authorities (i.e. Ministries competent for foodborne zoonoses and antimicrobial resistance: mainly ministries of public health and agriculture, and national food agencies). As such, the One Health EJP has a privileged position when it comes to feeding back its outcomes to national and European policy makers and risk managers.

Although research is an important element for the One Health EJP activities, it predominantly focuses on bringing together scientists interested in public health, animal health and food safety. The essential objective of the One Health EJP is to stimulate this inter-sector collaboration by building capacities, sharing methodologies, databases and surveillance data, harmonisation of procedures, etc.

Connecting to other international organizations and networks obviously reinforces the One Health EJP's scientific objectives, broadens the scope of the One Health approach, offers exciting opportunities for research and adds to the international and global visibility of the One Health EJP.

Purpose

One Health EJP has already active collaboration with ECDC and EFSA. One of its main focuses is antimicrobial resistance, and the One Health paradigm, on which the One Health EJP consortium is based, renders its activities potentially relevant also for European Medicines Agency EMA.

The purpose of this document is to give an overview on the possible impact work carried out in the One Health EJP can have for EMA, as preparation to contacting EMA representatives.

Identified needs

This document lists research and integrative needs of the potential stakeholder EMA, identified by WP5 by scanning open access documents considered most relevant for the topics antimicrobial resistance (AMR), foodborne zoonoses (FBZ) and emerging threats (ET). It also relates these needs with specific activities of One Health EJP Joint Integrative and Research projects (JIPs and JRPs) implemented during the first round of projects (2018-2020).

1. Column “EMA needs”

Here we listed the identified relevant research and integrative needs of EMA. The main procedure for the identification of needs is the scanning of online available documents (publications, reports, guidelines etc.) in the fields AMR, FBZ and ET published by the mentioned agency. The aim is to identify needs and knowledge gaps that have the potential to be closed by the ongoing or future work of One Health EJP. Attention is given to knowledge gaps requiring an intersectoral, multidisciplinary approach for their closure, i.e. a One Health approach.

2. Column “Highlights of One Health EJP JIPs and JRPs”

Each identified need is related with topics of joint research projects (JRP) or joint integrative projects (JIP) of the 1st round of One Health EJP that are dealing directly or indirectly with the mentioned need. The brief summary text highlights how One Health EJP is tackling the issue, and supports easy access to our website.

EMA identified need:	Highlights of One Health EJP JIPs and JRPs
One Health approach to address the issue of AMR [1-3].	<p>One Health EJP modus operandi. AMR is one of the three domains of One Health EJP, and research is undertaken by first round projects (2018-2020, listed below), as well as upcoming second round projects (2020-2022). The One Health EJP Glossary (developed by ORION, COHESIVE and NOVA) supports One Health cooperation.</p>
Cooperation and coordination at the international and global scale, to effectively tackle AMR [1, 3], including international regulatory convergence [2].	<p>One Health EJP focuses on European partnership, and we are building ties with the global stakeholders FAO, OIE and WHO. Some of our integrative projects are already investigating means to develop a European One Health policy guide (e.g. COHESIVE). ORION developed the OH Surveillance Codex - a high-level framework that supports mutual understanding and information exchange between OHS sectors. "Collaboration" is one of four core pillars in this framework and the OH Surveillance Codex already contains an idea catalogue for OH integration.</p>
Harmonised systems for monitoring antimicrobial resistance [3, 4], as well as increasing the availability of rapid and reliable diagnostics, including at the farm level, for AMR and pathogens [4].	<p>Given the participation of 19 European countries, and given the strong cross-sectoral prospective of One Health EJP, overarching work on harmonization and alignment of procedures and surveillance data (e.g. ORION) has high potential. The upcoming integrative project MATRIX will specifically address "harmonized systems for monitoring AMR".</p> <p>Moreover One Health EJP is in the frontline of developing fast, cost-sensitive, novel technologies for sampling (e.g. AIR SAMPLE) and AMR detection (e.g. IMPART, METASTAVA). Technologies range from metagenomic arrays (e.g. MAD-Vir) to pen-side methodologies (e.g. TOX detect), and focus on a range of bacteria like, but not restricted to, <i>Salmonella</i>, <i>Campylobacter</i>, <i>E. coli</i> (e.g. MoMIR-PPC) and <i>Klebsiella</i> (e.g. MedVetKlebs) and <i>C. difficile</i> (IMPART).</p> <p>In concordance with the One Health approach, all these methodologies are</p>

	harmonized at an early stage between sectors and across countries.
Development of novel antimicrobials and alternatives to antimicrobials, medicines as well as other therapeutic and prevention procedures, for animal use [1-4], and monitoring microbial susceptibility during and after such interventions [1]	Aiming at reducing the burden of AMR, One Health EJP research projects are investigating preventive and control measures to decrease the spread of pathogens without resorting to antimicrobials. These practices go from the use of nutraceutical products like pre- ad pro-biotics (e.g. MoMIR-PPC), to metagenomic approaches (e.g. ARDIG).
Optimization of use of antimicrobial consumption data, for example setting harmonized and more refined units of measurement [1, 4, 5]	Following strong interest of European stakeholders [2], One Health EJP members (e.g. ARDIG) are working on the harmonization of antimicrobial consumption and resistance data across borders and sectors. Specifically the ORION project developed the One Health Consensus Report Annotation Schema (OH-CRAS) that support the harmonized collection of OH Surveillance metadata (including units of measurement) across all sectors and that supports structured reporting of these metadata.
Increasing the responsibility of veterinarians at antimicrobial prescribing through training and education activities, as well as raising public awareness [4]	<p>One Health EJP organizes workshops, trainings, and communication activities with a specific focus on One Health. The summer schools, short-term missions and continuing professional development events are addressed at students, early career researchers, and professionals. Recently an interactive version of the Strategic Research Agenda was publicly released.</p> <p>In addition, the integrative and research projects organise focused trainings and workshops.</p>

References

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